

Comparison of Task Oriented Training and Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation Exercises in Diplegic Spastic Cerebral Palsy Patients

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Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Balance, Diplegic Spastic Cerebral palsy patients have difficulty in walking, demonstrate poor balance that Cerebral Palsy, Gait, Proprioceptive leads to poor gait and reaching movement as stability to all movements is Neuromuscular Facilitation Exercises, Task disturbed. Diplegic spastic cerebral palsy effects the lower extremity but also Oriented Training Exercises. upper extremity to some extent. The study aims to evaluate the comparison of Task Oriented training and Proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation exercises to improve gait, balance and function among patients. The study was a randomized clinical trial conducted at Children Hospital and Allied Hospital, Faisalabad, Pakistan. A sample of 40 participants were allocated in group A and B. Group A received Task oriented training exercises and Group B received Proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation exercises, with both groups undergoing three sessions per week for total 4 weeks. The groups were assessed at baseline using pediatric balance scale and modified Ashworth scale. Moreover, the data were analyzed using SPSS 27. At baseline Group A receiving TOET had (mean rank= 21.40) and (sum of ranks = 428.00) and Group B receiving PNF had (mean rank= 19.60) and (sum of ranks= 392.00). Post treatment, Group A receiving TOET had (mean rank= 24.64) and (sum of ranks= 443.50) and Group B receiving PNF had (mean rank= 12.36) and (sum of ranks= 222.50). After treatment Group A receiving TOET showed a much higher mean rank compared to Group B receiving PNF, suggesting significantly better balance improvements in group A compared to Group B. TOET had a significantly better result than PNF in improving mobility, gait, balance and functional activities.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Cerebral palsy (CP) has a heterogeneity of risk factors that are responsible for its occurrence as well as in clinical picturization, the extent of severity in functional limitations etc. (patel, 2020). The causes of cerebral are grouped into three segments antenatal, neonatal and postnatal among all these causes of cerebral palsy low birth weight and prematurity are most prevalent. Diplegic cerebral palsy is caused by abnormal development of brain's white matter before, during or soon after birth. (Salphale et al 2022).

Many methods are used in physiotherapy including casting, splinting, stretching, strengthening, posture, choosing an orthosis and movement facilitations. There are some interventions available for children with bilateral CP that concentrate on improving upper extremity functions. Bilateral CP patients being shown to get benefit from task-oriented training and lower extremity training. (Adiguzel et al 2024).

The effects of cerebral palsy vary, with some individuals needing walking assistance and others not, and some experiencing intellectual disabilities while others do not. Associated conditions can include epilepsy, blindness and deafness. While there is no cure, treatments can help improve functions, and the condition generally remains stable over time. (Alaxendar 2018). Spastic cerebral palsy affects children, causing stiffness muscle that can be located in the upper and lower body or both and on one or both sides. Spastic cerebral palsy is not a progressive condition, but it may take time to reach a diagnosis especially if symptoms are mild. In some cases, it can take months or years of observation before a clear diagnosis is made. Physical therapies often include stretching as a regular part of treatment to support better joint movement, reduce muscle stiffness, and enhance overall mobility. These exercises can be tailored to target specific muscle groups that may be tight or weakened due to spasticity. (Alexandar 2018)

It is observed PNF strengthening exercises are primarily used in lower extremities and considerably improve muscle strength, balance and gait. PNF integration pattern stimulates the proprioceptors within the muscles and tendon to enhance performance, flexibility and balance. It is generally effective in maximizing the reaction of exercise unit by increasing the coordination which reacts to stimulations in muscular strength and flexibility. (Rajalaxmi et al 2021).

2. METHODOLOGY

This study was a randomized clinical trial. This study was conducted at physiotherapy department of Allied hospital and Children hospital Faisalabad, Pakistan. The sample size of n=40 was taken according to the parent article (Kumar and ostwal 2016). Purposive sampling technique was used to collect the data. Participants were both male and female of different ages of 6 months to 8 years were included in study.

The researcher excluded participants with unstable seizures, receiving any treatment for spasticity or surgical procedure upto 3 months and presence of shortening of ankle, knee or hip joints that prevented children from keeping feet on ground. (kumar and ostwal 2016). Once the above mentioned inclusion and exclusion criteria was fulfilled, only eligible participants were included in this study. Written consent form was taken from each patient. Participants were randomized through lottery method. Number 1 allocated to group A and number 2 to Group B. Each participant was requested to draw either number 1 or 2 from the box. Group A was treated with task-oriented training exercises and Group B with Proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation exercises. The researcher collected the baseline data on the first visit. The researcher provided treatment according to the treatment plan for 4 weeks. Participants completed the questionnaire of PBS and MAS. Treatment then continued according to allocated groups. Patients were blinded but the physiotherapist who treated the patients was not blinded.

2.1 Common Treatment

Baseline treatment included an ultrasound and IR were applied on stiff muscles to relax them. Stretching were also done before starting the main protocol treatment.

2.2 Task-Oriented Training Exercises

Task based training for cerebral palsy aims to improve functional abilities through practice that focuses on every day tasks and activities. It involves repetitive practice of motor tasks to enhance motor learning and cortical reorganization. This approach works because it engages children in therapy, encourages them to complete tasks and help them to develop daily living skills. Task based training not only addresses functional impairments but also focuses on improving the ability to perform meaningful daily living activities. Goals and activities are tailored to each child's need abilities and interests. Tasks are practiced in context their children will be using these skills, such as at home or school. Repetitive practice of motor tasks helps the brain to recognize and strengthen neural pathways.

2.3 Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation Exercises

PNF techniques are used in physical therapy for children with cerebral palsy to improve muscle control, range of motion and strength. These techniques combine passive movement, active resistance and sometimes isometric contractions with the goal of enhancing the neuromuscular functions. PNF techniques can help to gain better control over muscles and movements, which can improve functional abilities. Repeated contractions and other PNF techniques help to increase muscle strength and endurance, allowing people to participate in activities more effectively. Some PNF techniques such as hold-relax, and contract-relax can help to reduce spasticity. Techniques such as rhythmic initiation and rhythmic stabilization can help improve coordination and balance, allowing the patients to move more fluidly and safely.

2.4 Data Analysis Procedure

The data was analyzed using SPSS(IBM) 27 parametric and nonparametric tests were decided after the assessment of normality.

2.4.1 Difference Between Groups

Mann-Whitney U test (nonparametric test) was used to compare two populations at different intervals.

3. RESULTS

The screening of 50 participants were done of whom, 40 were selected for study and allocated into two groups (Group A= 20, Group B= 20). 4 participants dropped out due to some personal reasons (two from group A and two from group B, resulting in an analysis of data from 36 participants).

The normality of data was tested through the Shapiro-Wilk test. The data of this study were not normally distributed as all of the pre treatment p values were less than 0.05. Hence, nonparametric tests were used for the analysis of data. Table 1 describes the age distribution of diplegic CP children in group A and B. In group A, mean age of the participants were 5.45 ± 0.60 years and in group B, mean age of the participants were 5.70 ± 0.65 years.

TABLE 1: DISTRIBUTION OF AGE

Groups	N	Mean±S.D	Minimum	Maximum
A	20	5.45±0.60	5	7
B	20	5.70±0.65	5	7

The distribution of genders of all the participants is displayed in table no. 4.2. It reveals that, Out of 20 participants in group A, 40 percent of the participants were men and 60 percent were women. In group B, 45% were males and 55 percent were females

TABLE 2: DISTRIBUTION OF GENDER

		f	%age	Valid %age
Group A	Males	8	20	40
	Females	12	30	60
	Total	20	50	100
Group B	Males	9	22.5	45

Females	11	27.5	55
Total	20	50	100

Table 3 shows the Ranks for Pre-treatment and Post-treatment PBS. N shows the sample size in each group. Mean rank shows the average rank of PBS scores for each group. The better the balance performance (higher PBS scores). Lower ranks indicate poorer balance performance (lower PBS scores). At baseline, group A receiving Task oriented training (TOT) had (Mean Rank = 21.40) and (Sum of Ranks = 428.00) and group B receiving Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation (PNF) had (Mean Rank = 19.60) and (Sum of Ranks = 392.00). Post-treatment, group A receiving Task oriented training (TOT) had (Mean Rank = 24.64) and (Sum of Ranks = 443.50) and group B receiving Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation (PNF) had (Mean Rank = 12.36) and (Sum of Ranks = 222.50). After treatment, Group A receiving Task oriented training (TOT) showed a much higher mean rank compared to Group B Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation (PNF), suggesting significantly better balance improvements in Group A compared to Group B.

TABLE 3: RANKS FOR PRE- AND POST-TREATMENT PEDIATRIC BALANCE SCALE (PBS) (MANN-WHITNEY U TEST)

	Groups	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
PBS (Pre-treatment)	A (TOT)	20	21.40	428.00
	B (PNF)	20	19.60	392.00
	Total	40		
PBS (Post-treatment)	A (TOT)	18	24.64	443.50
	B (PNF)	18	12.36	222.50
	Total	36		

4. DISCUSSION

The main purpose of this study was to determine the comparison of task-oriented training exercises and proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation exercises in diplegic spastic cerebral palsy patients. The results indicated that TOET contributed to more significant improvement in balance, gait and functional abilities.

In a study conducted by Hamidrica Azadi et al in 2020, on the effect of task-oriented training on functional mobility in children with cerebral palsy. The meta-analysis showed that task-oriented training had more significant effect on functional mobility than other conventional approaches in children with cerebral palsy. Task-oriented approach could be used as a treatment method in improving functional mobility in children with cerebral palsy. The findings of this study is consistent with the results of our research. (Azadi et al, 2020)

In 2020 study conducted by Walaa E. et al investigated the effects of Task-oriented on balance in children with cerebral palsy. The findings of this study suggest that incorporating task-oriented training into rehabilitation program can be an effective strategy for improving balance in children with spastic cerebral palsy, supporting its potential use as an adjunct to conventional therapy. These studies support the current study research findings, as the results are according to previous literature.

Sri Laxmi et al 2024 conducted a study on the efficacy of both Task-oriented training and PNF exercises in enhancing upper extremities functions in children with spastic CP. Task-oriented training, incorporating daily and play activities not only improves motivation but also active participation. PNF exercises featuring diagonal patterns proved effective in improving dysfunction in affected arm. (Sri laxmi et al 2024).

All the literature review indicates the effectiveness of TOET in improving balance, gait and functional activities. According to the researcher there is a lack of studies that uses TOET for cerebral palsy patients. Both interventions provide the basic comprehensive treatment protocol for children suffering from diplegic cerebral palsy patients. Previous literature proved

the importance of TOET intervention can significantly improve patient's daily living activities.

There are several limitations of the study. Firstly, some parents were over worried to give information as they felt vulnerable and exhausted while describing the symptoms of their children. Secondly, it is challenging to maintain long term follow up with patients throughout the study. Handling children and instructing them to perform activities posed significant challenges in this study. For future research, it is recommended to conduct study with a longer follow up period and a large sample size to better assess the effectiveness and retention of the intervention.

4.1 CONCLUSION

The study concluded that Task-oriented training exercises exhibited a statistically significant improvement in functional impacts and activity level, as compared to Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation exercises.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data associated with this study will be provided by the corresponding author upon request.

FUNDING DETAILS

No funding has been received for this research.

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